

22NRM03 “Metrology to support standardisation of hydrogen fuel sampling for heavy duty hydrogen transport”

Report A2.1.1

SELECTION OF HYDROGEN SAMPLING STRATEGIES FOR HD-HRS

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Submission date of the deliverable/report: 22nd November 2023

Revision date of the deliverable/report: -

Summary

This report was written as part of activity A2.1.1 from the Partnership on Metrology project “Metrology to support standardisation of hydrogen fuel sampling for heavy duty hydrogen transport” (MetHyTrucks). The three-year European project started 1st June 2023.

This report describes summarily the three hydrogen sampling strategies (using three different devices to be considered for sampling hydrogen at heavy duty hydrogen refuelling stations) which will be used in the other activities of the project MetHyTrucks and describes the steps needed to adapt the sampling equipment (for the ENGIE sampling device and the HySam device), which is used in these strategies, to the conditions prevailing at HD-HRS. The third device (one of the two devices that NPL is acquiring) has been developed for HD conditions.

This report was written by:

Name	Institution	E-Mail
Karine Arrhenius	RISE	Karine.arrhenius@ri.se
Thomas Bacquart	NPL	Thomas.bacquart@npl.co.uk
Sven Kaiser	ZBT	s.kaiser@zbt.de
Maxime Dufond	ENGIE	maxime.dufond@engie.com
Thor Aarhaug	SINTEF	thor.a.aarhaug@sintef.no

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1 Introduction

Hydrogen can significantly contribute to reducing emissions from the transportation sector as it is particularly well suited as a fuel for long-haul heavy-duty (HD) vehicles. The uptake of hydrogen for heavy-duty transport requires further standardisation to support Europe's green energy future. Sampling systems and methods have already been developed for use at hydrogen refuelling stations (HRS) for light-duty (LD) vehicles, however there is a lack of technical evidence for heavy-duty transport.

The project MetHyTrucks [1] will adapt existing, or develop new, sampling systems for HD applications. This is the first step that will be needed to enable the collection of a representative sample of hydrogen at these emerging stations. Sampling methodologies have been developed and tested in EMPIR 19ENG04 MetroHyVe 2 [2] at refuelling stations, but these sampling methodologies are solely for light-duty applications. Either these methodologies need to be adapted or new ones developed for HD, as some of the station's parameters differ.

The goal of this report is to describe summarily the three hydrogen sampling strategies (using three different devices to be considered for sampling hydrogen at heavy duty hydrogen refuelling stations) which will be used in the other activities of the project MetHyTrucks and to describe the steps needed to adapt the sampling equipment, which is used in these strategies, to the conditions prevailing at HD-HRS.

2 Definition of the sampling strategies

In this report, we focus solely on sampling strategies for gaseous species.

The definition of the different sampling strategies is taken from the review published recently [3]

Two main groups of strategies are described. The first group is called in the article "gas parallel" strategies and the other "gas serial" strategies. Both strategies groups concern sampling at the HRS nozzle.

"Gas serial": in these strategies, the sample is taken directly into a sampling cylinder. These sampling systems imply to manage the hydrogen fuel conditions and may require operating the HRS in service mode. The sampling system may also include a tank allowing to not override the protocol of the station.

The following strategies are described in the article:

- ASTM D7606-7 method
- Air Liquide sampling device
- Japanese approach
- ENGIE sampling device

“Gas parallel”: in these strategies, a tee-connection is used to parallelly fill the sampling cylinder and a FCEV or a receptacle (larger than the sampling cylinder). These strategies do not require to bypass the safety protocol of the station.

The following strategies are described in the article:

- Methods using the Linde qualitizer
- Hy-SaM sampling device

3 Selection of the sampling strategies

For the upcoming activities of MetHyTrucks, three devices are planned to be used for sampling at HD HRS. The sections below described in short, the devices selected.

3.1 ENGIE sampling device

To sample at the HRS nozzle, ENGIE has developed a device adaptable for stations delivering hydrogen fuel both at 350 and 700 bar and which also allows to perform online analysis of oxygen and water during a refuelling event. On the contrary to the other “gas serial methods, this method doesn't require the overriding of the safety protocol of the station. ENGIE has planned to adapt their system to HD-HRS.

3.2 Hy-SaM sampling device

Within the German Hy-Lab project, ZBT and ZSW developed a sampling device called Hy-SaM which allows sampling according to the ISO19880-1 [4] and SAE J2601 [5] without overriding the refueling protocol. It also offers the possibility of venting to atmosphere rather than using a FCEV. ZBT has planned to adapt their system to HD-HRS.

3.3 NPL DirSam (ASTM D7606-7) method

Within NPL internal project, a new sampling system has been developed as direct sampling strategy. This method is following the principles described in the standard ASTM D7606-17 [6]. The sampling is performed at the nozzle and venting of hydrogen to atmosphere is performed through an exhaust stack. The sampling device is referred to as the NPL Hydrogen direct sampling apparatus (NPL DirSam). The method is adaptable for stations delivering hydrogen fuel both at 350 and 700 bar and is capable of up to 120 g/s (high flow). It comes with 5-m flexible line connected to a tripod for atmospheric

ventilation. The flow to the cylinders is adjustable using a flow metering valves. The cylinder for sampling is 10L aluminum cylinder with DIN 477 N.1 valve.

3.4 NPL HD-ParSam (Heavy duty hydrogen parallel sampling)

Within NPL internal project, a new sampling system has been developed as parallel sampling strategy. The new system developed is a sampling device called HD-ParSam which allows sampling according to the ISO19880-1 and SAE J2601 without overriding the refueling protocol. It also offers the possibility of venting to atmosphere with its own sampling vent rather than using a FCEV. The method is adaptable for stations delivering hydrogen fuel both at 350 and 700 bar and is capable of up to 120 g/s (high flow). The system will be completed and delivered to NPL in December 2023.

4 Steps to adapt the sampling strategies

The following sections describe the activities needed to adapt the sampling strategies which were developed for LD applications to HD conditions.

4.1 ENGIE sampling device

The ENGIE device has been fitted with a receptacle able to plug 350 barg HDV nozzle. No modification of the device is required for pressure or flow. The device was originally designed and qualified to support pressure up to 875 barg. The tank volume of the ENGIE's device of 55L and the valves could also originally support flow rate until 120g/s.

As the smallest tank volume implemented in the table of the HDV 350 barg HF filling protocols (CEP/WENGER) is around 835 liter, the current volume of the tank does not allow the station to deliver hydrogen without by-passing the safety protocol. New protocols are in preparation and will, maybe, include tank volume around 420L. To be able to sample without by-passing the safety protocol, the volume of tank must be increased and to that effect, the whole bench must be redesigned in order to get enough space to fit this much bigger tank. Sampling device and tank is designed to be used from -40 to +80°C. The sampling protocol need to ensure that the temperature of hydrogen will be between these limits.

ENGIE brings his own venting mast on-site for the sampling. It consists on a stainless steel mast of 3 m height connected to the sampling device through a 10 m stainless steel flexible hose. This solution allows to safely vent hydrogen contained into the tank after the sampling. The tank is PED (pressure equipment directive) certified and need to be inerted before transport. This step could be eliminated by using instead a TPED (transport pressure equipment directive) tank.

4.2 Hy-SaM sampling device

The HySam device has originally been developed to sample from 700 bar refuelling stations. In conformity to SAE, it is pressure-resistant up to 875 bar. The system is divided into three modules. Module 1 contains all parts for simultaneously sampling up to three cylinders (2.25 or 10 l). Module 2 is the mobile vent. Module 3 contains a buffer tank including the necessary safety components. By

using module 2, sampling can be performed without refuelling a FCEV. Optionally, the vent lines (including safety relief valves) from modules 1 and 3 can be connected to module 2 or to the HRS vent line. Also optional is the simultaneous sampling for particles. To adapt the system to HD-HRS, a new line will be added for sampling at 350 bar. The 350 bar hardware is suitable for minimal hydrogen temperatures of -20 °C. With the new design, it will be possible to sample from 700 bar and 350 bar refuelling lines.

A receptacle is being added to the Hy-Sam device to accommodate sampling at HD HRS (350 bar). The sizes of the pipings have also been increased to support high flow (up to 120 g/s). An added switch valve can be used to direct the gas into the correct pressure line (350 or 700 bar). While performing a parallel sampling (e.g. with a FCEV), the new device is compatible with all protocols for HD up to 120 g/s. The device does not need to be modified for the venting operations.

4.3 NPL DirSam (ASTM D7606-7) method and NPL HD-ParSam (Heavy duty hydrogen parallel sampling)

The systems NPL DirSam and NPL HD-ParSam are designed for heavy duty sampling and therefore planned to operate up to 120 g/s, pressure up to 350 bar for heavy duty. The system is compatible 700 bar low flow.

5 Conclusion

The devices selected are the ENGIE sampling device, the HySam device, and one of the devices from NPL (either the NPL DirSam or the NPL HD-ParSam). The report presents the steps needed to adapt the ENGIE sampling device and the HySam device to HD conditions. The third system has been designed for HD.

6 References

- [1] *Metrology to support standardisation of hydrogen fuel sampling for heavy duty hydrogen transport*, 22NRM03: EURAMET, 2023-2026.
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- [3] K. Arrhenius, T. Aarhaug, T. Bacquart, A. Morris, S. Bartlett, L. Wagner, C. Blondeel, B. Gozlan, Y. Lescornez, N. Chramosta, C. Spitta, E. Basset, Q. Nouvelot and M. Rizand, "Strategies for the sampling of hydrogen at refuelling stations for purity assessment," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 46, no. 70, pp. 34839-34853, 2021.